

Voice Stick: An Innovative Idea for an Economical, User-Friendly and Portable E-book Reader for Visually Impaired

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Abstract – *In today's world communication has become so easy due to integration of communication technologies. The visually challenged people cannot read books on their own which decreases their independency. This project aims at developing a book reader system that will help the visually impaired people to recognize the contents of the books they want to read. The system will not lead the user make use of mouse. Instead this technology uses only special keys on the keyboard, text converts to audio format, etc. Also, this system can be used by any normal person. For example, the one who is not able to read. The interaction with the system is completely based on voice response which will make it user friendly and efficient to use. This saves time and energy.*

Keywords: *Book reader, voice to text conversion, text to speech conversion.*

I. Introduction

The visually impaired, who make up a large section of the population, face many problems when it comes to accessing one of the most widespread means of knowledge, books. There are a very few books that exist in the Braille format for the visually impaired to read. And with one page in a normal book taking up to three pages in a Braille book [1], they are very large and heavy. If this medium of access to knowledge and entertainment could be made less cumbersome, cheaper and simpler, a large section of the blind population would have an easier access to education, thus increasing their currently poor literacy rate. The best way to tackle this would be to take the help of technology. To achieve the goal in the sense-and to the extent-that a blind user can himself read different printed materials without unreasonable expenditures of time and effort; moreover, there is a reasonable expectation that reading machines will become affordable by individual users. There have been many proposed methods to the reading machine problem. The major shortcomings are that reading is very slow and much training is required to learn the machine's "language." The Voice stick book reader comprises of different modules, which deal with the functioning of its different features. The books can be stored as pdf files in the system. The name of the books stored is prompted and the blind user can select the book he wants to read. For the selection process the special keys in the keyboard is used. The use of the special keys is also prompted. A user can read from the point where he stopped last time or can read from the start itself. There are also keys to pause the reading or to exit from reading. Thus, voice

stick is a user friendly economic book reader for the blinds. Text to speech synthesis is the automatic conversion of a text into speech that resembles, as closely as possible, a native speaker of the language reading that text. Text-to speech synthesizer is the technology which lets computer speak to you. The text to speech [7] system gets the text as the input and then a computer algorithm which called text to speech engine analyses the text, pre-processes the text and synthesizes the speech with some mathematical models. The text to speech engine usually generates sound data in an audio format as the output.

II. Historical Review

The first computer-based speech-synthesis systems originated in the late 1950s. Noriko Umeda et al. developed the first general English text-to-speech system in 1968 at the Electrotechnical Laboratory, Japan [6]. Early electronic speech-synthesizers sounded robotic and were often barely intelligible. The quality of synthesized speech has steadily improved, but as of 2016 output from contemporary speech synthesis systems remains clearly distinguishable from actual human speech. Kurzweil predicted in 2005 that as the cost-performance ratio caused speech synthesizers to become cheaper and more accessible, more people would benefit from the use of text-to-speech programs [7]. The primary disadvantage of the system was the need for specially prepared materials, a limitation that also flawed other reading systems proposed during the following three decades.

III. Proposed System

The books can be inserted into the system as pdf, which can be included into eBook files. Once detected, the device plays an audio notification and then, the user can speak the name of either the file or the author. The speech input, when recognized, is used to search for the file in the system. If the file is found, which has the same name as what the user spoke, it is said to be 'match' and the device plays another tone indicating that the file has been found successfully and the display is now active for the user to access. Even though, the speech input does not match any file present in the system, a notification will be played indicating that the user should repeat the query. Else the system will notify that the file is not available in the memory. The system also provides some facilities such as reading another file, reading the previous page in the file, and reading the next page. If the visually impaired user wishes to read another file, it can be done at any point of time by using the button provided and repeating the entire process again.

Fig.1 System Design

Voice stick totally works by using the special keys in the keyboard such as space bar, shift, control, escape, enter, etc. For selecting the book, control key is used. If the user wants to skip something while playing the audio, escape can be used. Initially user can search for any book. If it is present, it will be played accordingly. If it is not present then a notification showing the unavailability of book will be played. If the user wants to go for a book which is already present in the system, then he can skip all above procedures and play a notification showing which all books are present in the system. If a book is selected, it will be played. There is also a provision to pause the audio and then after sometime, the paused audio can be continued. Even though the user exits from voice stick and enter into it some other time, the paused audio can be played without any hindrance. Figure 1 shows the design of the system [1].

A text to speech system or engine is composed of two parts: a front-end and a backend. The front-end has two major tasks. First, it converts raw text containing symbols like numbers and abbreviations into the equivalent of written-out words. This process is often

called text normalization [2], pre-processing, or tokenization. The front-end then assigns phonetic transcriptions to each word, and divides and marks the text into prosodic units, like phrases, clauses, and sentences. The process of assigning phonetic transcriptions [5] to words is called text-to-phoneme or grapheme to phoneme conversion. Phonetic transcriptions [5] and prosody information together make up the symbolic linguistic representation [4] that is output by the front-end. The back end often referred to as the synthesizer then converts the symbolic linguistic representation into sound. In certain systems, this part includes the computation of the target prosody pitch contour, phoneme durations, which is then imposed on the output speech. Many TTS systems are developed based on the principle, corpus-based speech synthesis. It is very popular for its high quality and natural speech output.

III.1. Architecture of TTS

The TTS system comprises of these 5 fundamental

- Text Analysis and Detection
- Text Normalization and Linearization
- Phonetic Analysis
- Prosodic Modeling and Intonation
- Acoustic Processing

Input text is passed through these phases to obtain the speech. Text analysis part is pre-processing part which analyses the input text and organizes it into manageable list of words. It consists of numbers, abbreviations, acronyms and transforms them into full text when needed. Text normalization is the transformation of text to pronounceable form. The main objective of this process is to identify punctuation marks and pauses between words. Usually the text normalization process is done for converting all letters of lowercase or upper case, to remove punctuations, accent marks, stop words or too common words from letters.

Phonetic analysis converts the orthographical symbols into phonological ones. The concept of prosody is the combination of stress pattern, rhythm and intonation in a speech. The modelling describes the speaker's emotion. Recent investigations suggest the identification of the vocal features which signal emotional content may help to create a very natural synthesized speech. The voice will be generated according to the voice characteristics of a person. There are three type of Acoustic synthesizing available

- i. Concatenative Synthesis
- ii. Formant Synthesis
- iii. Articulatory Synthesis

The concatenation of pre-recorded human voice is called Concatenative synthesis, in this process a database is needed having all the pre-recorded words. The natural sounding speech is the main advantage and the main drawback is the using and developing of large database. Formant-synthesized speech can be constantly intelligible. It does not have any database of speech

samples. So, the speech is artificial and robotic. Speech organs are called Articulators. In this articulatory synthesis techniques for synthesizing speech based on models of the human vocal tract are to be developed. It produces a complete synthetic output, typically based on mathematical models.

Fig. 2.TTS Architecture

IV. Conclusion

Voice stick was tested by taking five ebooks, and after selecting the file, the contents of the file were displayed correctly. Hence it can be said that the complete system, with some technical improvements, which will enhance the system performance, is realizable. Besides, as the materials used for building the prototype were inexpensive, it can be said that the final product will be affordable. The proposed system will help in overcoming drawbacks that are faced by the blind people in reading books. Eliminated the concept of using mouse click shortcuts along with screen readers. The user only needs to follow the instructions given by the IVR and use of certain keys accordingly to get the respective services offered. Prompting messages improve system efficiency. User free to click blandly anywhere on the screen.

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